

Impact of SaO₂/Fio₂ Delta Value on Mortality in Critically Ill Patients with ARDS and COVID-19 in Prone Position

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The COVID 19 pandemic generated in December 2019 has come to change paradigms in terms of ventilatory support measures worldwide, continuous clinical monitoring allows timely decision making impacting mortality in patients with ARDS.

Objective: To identify the relationship between the SO₂/FiO₂ delta and mortality in critically ill patients with ARDS and COVID-19 in prone position.

Material and methods: Retrospective, observational, comparative, analytical study, where all patients who met the inclusion criteria were evaluated: under mechanical ventilation and prone position for acute respiratory failure secondary to SARS-CoV-2 infection, measuring the value of SO₂/FiO₂ before and after the change of position to prone position, also mortality was recorded.

Results: A total of 74 patients were analyzed, 33 corresponding to the survivors and 41 to the non-survivors group. The median age was 53.5 ± 12.77, with a male predominance. The mean days of mechanical ventilation were 10.64 ± 5.16. A ROC curve was also performed for Δ SaO₂/FiO₂ and survival (AUC 0.668, p=0.013) for predicting patient survival.

Conclusion: Continuous clinical monitoring is necessary to optimize resources in the different hospital and out-of-hospital areas. Δ SO₂/FiO₂ can be very useful for the continuous monitoring and prognosis in COVID-19 critical patients.

KEYWORDS: SaO₂/FiO₂ delta value, ARDS, COVID-19, prone position, critically ill patient.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The SARS-CoV-2 virus causing Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) was declared a pandemic since the World Health Organization (WHO) decree on March 11, 2020, and has infected more than 118,147,420 people and caused 2,621,170 deaths as of March 09, 2021 ⁽¹⁾.

The most common initial symptoms of coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) disease are cough, fever, fatigue, headache, myalgia, and diarrhea ⁽²⁾. It is within the first 7 days after the onset of symptoms that severe disease usually occurs. Dyspnea is the most common symptom of severe disease and is usually accompanied by hypoxemia ^(3, 4). Most patients with severe COVID-19 develop progressive respiratory failure shortly after the onset of dyspnea and hypoxemia, eventually developing

acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), due to the acute onset of bilateral infiltrates, severe hypoxemia and the presence of pulmonary edema without cardiac cause or fluid overload ⁽⁵⁾. Most patients with severe COVID-19 have lymphopenia ⁽⁶⁾ and some have thromboembolic complications ⁽⁷⁾, as well as central or peripheral nervous system disorders ⁽⁸⁾. Severe COVID-19 can also cause acute cardiac, renal, and hepatic injury, as well as cardiac arrhythmias, rhabdomyolysis, coagulopathy, and shock ^(9, 10). These organ failures may be associated with clinical and laboratory signs of inflammation, which include fever, thrombocytopenia, increased C-reactive protein, and interleukin-6.

The ARDS that these patients may develop requires adequate monitoring which includes multiple arterial punctures

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or can be done through a continuous arterial line, which sometimes is not available in all medical units, so delta SaO₂/FiO₂ is proposed as a marker for noninvasive monitoring.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This is an observational, retrospective and comparative study. It was conducted at the Intensive Care Unit of the Hospital de Especialidades Médicas No. 1 (UMAE T1, Bajío), Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social (IMSS).

All patients admitted to the intensive care unit who met the inclusion criteria (patients with ARDS and COVID19 over 18 years and prone position) in a period from April 1, 2021 to September 30, 2021 were included. The sample was taken on a non-probabilistic convenience basis.

On admission, all patients with a diagnosis of acute respiratory distress syndrome with SARS-CoV-2 infection with positive PCR test who were admitted to the Intensive Care Unit of UMAE HE No.1 Bajío and who required mechanical ventilation and prone position were evaluated according to selection criteria.

Patient demographics were recorded, and the delta value was calculated, according to medical and nursing records, within one hour before and after the prone position. All the patients were followed up until their discharge from the unit to record mortality in intensive care, designating non-survivors as cases and survivors as controls.

The primary objective was to identify the relationship between the SaO₂/FiO₂ delta and mortality in critically ill patients with ARDS and COVID-19 in prone position.

Statistical analysis

The information was processed using the SPSS program. The results are presented in frequency distribution tables and graphs to facilitate their evaluation. Descriptive statistics were used to obtain measures of central tendency (mean, standard deviation and range for discrete variables and frequencies for nominal variables). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was performed.

Comparison of groups (survivors vs no-survivors) for qualitative variables was performed using χ^2 (or Fisher's exact test as appropriate) and for quantitative variables with Student t-test.

The value of $p < 0.05$ is taken for statistical significance. The present study is considered No Research Risk in accordance with the regulations of the general health law on health research. After signing the informed consent, it was explained to them that this is a study that aims to know the attitudes of the workers in their work area, safeguarding their data and without interventions derived from the results of the questionnaire. This work was carried out with the approval of the ethics and institutional research committees with registration number: **R-2020-3609-007**.

III. RESULTS

A total of 74 patients were analyzed, 33 corresponding to the non-survivors and 41 to the survivor group.

The median age was 53.5 ± 12.77 , with a male predominance of %. The most frequent comorbidity was arterial hypertension (40%) followed by type 2 diabetes (34%). The mean days of mechanical ventilation were 10.64 ± 5.16 . The oxygenation variables are explained in Table 1.

In the comparison between groups (survivors vs non-survivors), no significant differences were found between demographic variables such as age, sex and BMI. With respect to comorbidities, although type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease were present in greater numbers in the group of non-survivors, but no significant p values were found.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics

Age (years)	53.5 ± 12.77
<i>Gender n(%)</i>	
Male	47 (63%)
Female	27 (37%)
Weight (Kg)	84.89 ± 15.79
Height (m)	1.65 ± 0.09
MCI (kg/m ²)	31 ± 4.71
<i>Comorbidities</i>	
Diabetes mellitus type 2, n (%)	25 (34%)
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	30 (40%)
Asthma	1 (1.5%)
COPD	9 (12%)
<i>Oxygenation parameters</i>	
SO ₂ before prone position (pre)	87.43 ± 9.20
FiO ₂ (%) pre	91.8 ± 15.12
SO ₂ /FiO ₂ pre	99.06 ± 25.61
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ pre	90.21 ± 30.39
SO ₂ after prone position (post)	94.39 ± 2.98
FiO ₂ (%) post	60.47 ± 17.77
SO ₂ /FiO ₂ post	169.57 ± 49.35
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ post	162.93 ± 65.15
Delta SO ₂ /FiO ₂	70.50 ± 45.19
Mechanical ventilation (days)	10.64 ± 5.16

Values are means \pm standard deviation (SD)

When analyzing oxygenation parameters, although the mean peripheral saturation and SO₂/FiO₂ ratio as well as PaO₂/FiO₂ prior to prone position were higher in non-survivors vs. survivors no significant difference was reported. However, after the prone position, the inspired oxygen fraction was lower in the surviving patients ($p = 0.03$), and a higher value was found in the SO₂/FiO₂ ratio ($p = 0.03$) and PaO₂/FiO₂ ($p = 0.04$) in the group of the survivors with respect to the non-survivors.

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Surviving patients remained more days under mechanical ventilation (p= 0.02) (Table 2).

Table.2 Baseline characteristics according to allocated group

	Non-survivors (n= 33)	Survivors (n= 41)	p- value
Age (years)	56.36 ± 10.95	51.20 ± 13.76	0.07 ^a
Gender n(%)			
Male	20 (61%)	27 (66%)	
Female	13 (39%)	14 (35%)	0.8 ^b
Weight (Kg)	85.02 ± 13.62	84.79 ± 17.52	0.95 ^a
Height (m)	1.65 ± 0.01	1.64 ± 0.09	0.95 ^a
MCI (kg/m2)	31.04 ± 4.58	30.98 ± 4.87	0.95 ^a
<i>Comorbidities</i>			
Diabetes mellitus type 2, n (%)	15 (45%)	10 (25%)	0.05 ^b
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	13 (40%)	17 (42%)	0.85 ^b
Asthma	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0.36 ^b
COPD	5 (15%)	4 (9%)	0.72 ^b
<i>Oxygenation parameters</i>			
SO ₂ before prone position (pre)	88.42 ± 6.65	86.93 ± 10.84	0.4 ^a
FiO ₂ pre	91.76 ± 14.59	91.83 ± 15.72	0.98 ^a
SO ₂ /FiO ₂ pre	99.50 ± 22	98.72 ± 28.46	0.89 ^a
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ pre	91.64 ± 26.57	89.05 ± 33.44	0.71 ^a
SO ₂ after prone position (post)	94.21 ± 3.51	94.54 ± 2.52	0.64 ^a
FiO ₂ post	65.30 ± 18.41	56.59 ± 16.44	0.03 ^{a,c}
SO ₂ /FiO ₂ post	156.13 ± 45.92	180.39 ± 49.88	0.03 ^{a,c}
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ post	149.99 ± 92.18	173.35 ± 45.77	0.04 ^{a,c}
Δ SO ₂ /FiO ₂	56.63 ± 41.84	81.66 ± 41.17	0.01 ^{a,c}
Mechanical ventilation (days)	9.12 ± 4.92	11.90 ± 5	0.02 ^{a,c}

Plus-minus values are means ± standard deviation (SD); ^a t-test ; ^b chi-squared test; ^c significant p-value

A ROC curve was performed for ΔSO₂/FiO₂ and survival, finding an AUC of 0.668 (p= 0.013, 95% CI 0.543-0.793) (Fig.1).

For the SO₂/FiO₂ ratio prior to prone position the values found in the ROC analysis were AUC 0.483 (p= 0.802 CI95% 0.350-0.616), however for the SO₂/FiO₂ ratio after prone

position AUC of 0.647 (p= 0.030 CI95% 0.520-0.775) was reported (Fig.2).

IV. DISCUSSION

During the pandemic secondary to the SARS-CoV-2 virus disease, more than 118,147,420 was infected⁽¹⁾. The main initial symptoms are cough, fever, fatigue, headache, myalgia and diarrhea⁽²⁾, and the main symptom of severe disease is dyspnea accompanied by hypoxemia^(3, 4), even developing Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS), which is characterized by the acute appearance of bilateral infiltrates, severe/severe hypoxemia and presence of pulmonary edema without cardiac cause or fluid overload⁽⁵⁾, PaO₂/FiO₂ (PF) ratio ≤200. For which arterial puncture is necessary either continuously or by means of continuous invasive monitoring lines, not being available in all services and even with shortage within the critical medicine services during the peaks of the pandemic.

International literature mentions that patients with severe COVID-19 may develop lymphopenia, thromboembolic complications, central or peripheral nervous system involvement, acute cardiac, renal and hepatic lesions, rhabdomyolysis, coagulopathy and shock⁽⁶⁻¹⁰⁾; these organ failures may be associated with clinical and laboratory signs of inflammatory response. The development of lung injury leading to respiratory dysfunction and/or failure leading even to the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome⁽⁶⁻¹⁰⁾.

It has been shown that the pulse oximetry saturation ratio SatO₂/FiO₂ (SF) can be a reliable noninvasive alternative to the PF ratio⁽¹¹⁻¹³⁾. In addition, it has been described that patients with COVID-19 reach oxygen levels incompatible with life without the presence of dyspnea, which was called silent hypoxemia, defying basic biology⁽¹⁴⁾.

There are several sociodemographic factors that influence the severity of SARS-COV-2 disease, within our study

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we identified as main ones the history of arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, immunosuppression, obesity and male sex, which corresponds with the current international literature, as mentioned by David A. Berlin in his article on Severe COVID published in 2020 in the NEJM journal ⁽¹⁵⁾.

The mean age of the patients in the non-survivors was 56.36 ± 10.95 years while the survivor group was 51.20 ± 13.76 years, without statistical significance with a $p=0.007$, which does not coincide with what is mentioned in most of the current literature. The number of days of mechanical ventilation in the non-survivors was 9.12 ± 4.92 vs 11.90 ± 5 in survivors group reaching an important statistical significance ($p=0.021$), coinciding with the current literature. Justified under the precept that those patients who survived required more time under invasive ventilation until weaning.

Due to the critical nature of tissue oxygen consumption in the body, continuous monitoring of SO_2 is essential, having an important accuracy that allows clinical decision making ⁽¹⁶⁻¹⁸⁾. In this study, most patients had an average SO_2 of 89%, with a range up to 45-100%, with a FiO_2 contribution of 100%. Allowing rapid decision making helping to improve the prognosis of our patients with ARDS due to COVID.

Patient oxygenation is initially assessed with a pulse oximeter. Oxygen saturation measured by pulse oximetry (SpO_2) may differ from true SO_2 by up to $\pm 4\%$ ⁽¹⁹⁾.

The ratio of oxygen saturation to fraction of inspired oxygen (SO_2/FiO_2) has been validated as a surrogate marker for the ratio of oxygen partial pressure to fraction of inspired oxygen (PaO_2/FiO_2) in mechanically ventilated patients with ARDS ⁽²⁰⁾. SO_2/FiO_2 ratios of 235 and 315 correlates with PaO_2/FiO_2 ratios of 200 and 300, respectively ⁽²¹⁾. In a prospective study, performed in cardiac revascularization surgery patients, PaO_2/FiO_2 values correlated in the diagnosis of ARDS, a PaO_2/FiO_2 of 300 correlated with a SO_2/FiO_2 of 311 (Sensitivity 90%, Specificity 80%). Allowing with SO_2/FiO_2 an early real-time identification of ARDS, as well as reducing the cost ⁽²²⁾.

The SO_2/FiO_2 ratio may be a reliable tool for the detection of hypoxemia among patients admitted to the emergency department, particularly during the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak ^(23,24). Within this study in patients the average first PaO_2/FiO_2 was 91.64 ± 26.57 and the average first SO_2/FiO_2 was 99.50 ± 22 , demonstrating the close relationship between the two and agreeing with international literature.

In this study, we were able to identify the relationship between the Delta of SO_2/FiO_2 and the change to prone position with respect to the prognosis of patients with ARDS due to COVID 19 in the Intensive Care Unit. Xiaofan Lu, et al. in their article published in Respiratory Research in 2020 demonstrated that SO_2/FiO_2 can be useful as a prognostic marker since it is non-invasive and facilitates immediate treatment adjustment, thus improving overall survival ⁽²⁵⁻²⁷⁾.

On finding a relationship between the Delta SaO_2/FiO_2 value and mortality, a ROC curve was performed for $\Delta SO_2/FiO_2$ and survival, finding an AUC of 0.669 with $p=0.013$. The importance of the SO_2/FiO_2 index lies in the immediate and

continuous identification of the response to interventions and changes in management, allows us to have an overview of the prognosis of the patient with ARDS secondary to SARS-COV-2 pneumonia, and also allows us to save and optimize the available resources.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Continuous clinical monitoring takes on great importance during the pandemic secondary to COVID-19, where it is necessary to optimize resources in the different hospital and out-of-hospital areas. $\Delta SO_2/FiO_2$ can be very useful for the continuous monitoring and prognosis of patients. Post-prone delta SaO_2/FiO_2 may become a predictive assessment of mortality in patients who develop ARDS from COVID-19.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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